

MATLAB usage and practices

The purpose of this survey is to collect feedback from users of MATLAB and similar languages (Octave, Scilab, Rlab, etc.) regarding how these languages are being used.

Your participation in this research study is voluntary. If you decide to participate, you may withdraw at any time.

We will keep your information confidential, with all data being stored in a password protected electronic format. Additionally, the surveys will not contain any information that could personally identify you. The results of this study will only be used for scholarly purposes and may be shared in papers of the specialty.

For any questions you might have concerning this survey, please do not hesitate to contact us via email at er.reis@campus.fct.unl.pt.

***Required**

1. Where did you hear about this survey? *

Mark only one oval.

- E-mail
- LinkedIn
- MATLAB Central
- Reddit
- ResearchGate
- GNU Octave Discourse
- Word of mouth

This section concerns your programming experience.

2. Programming is my primary professional activity. *

Mark only one oval.

	1	2	3	4	5	
Strongly disagree	<input type="radio"/>	Strongly agree				

3. What status do you currently identify with the most? *

Mark only one oval.

- Fully employed by a company / organisation
- Partially employed by a company / organisation
- Self-employed (earning income directly from their own business or trade)
- Freelancer (pursuing a profession without a long-term commitment to an employer)
- Teacher
- Student
- Researcher
- Retired
- Other

4. How many years of experience do you have with programming in general? *

Mark only one oval.

- Less than 1 year
- Between 1 and 4 years
- Between 4 and 7 years
- Between 7 and 10 years
- More than 10 years

5. How many years of experience do you have with MATLAB or a similar language? *

Mark only one oval.

- Less than 1 year
- Between 1 and 4 years
- Between 4 and 7 years
- Between 7 and 10 years
- More than 10 years

6. Which of the following programming languages (MATLAB and similar languages) do you use? *

Select one or more options.

Tick all that apply.

MATLAB

Octave

Scilab

RLab

Other: _____

7. Rate your level of experience with MATLAB. *

Mark only one oval.

	1	2	3	4	5	
Trainee	<input type="radio"/>	Expert				

8. What programming language do you use the most? *

9. Rate your level of experience with the programming language you use the most. *

Mark only one oval.

	1	2	3	4	5	
Trainee	<input type="radio"/>	Expert				

10. What other programming languages do you use, if any?

11. For what do you use MATLAB or similar languages? *

Select one or more options.

Tick all that apply.

- Data Analytics
- Machine Learning
- Signal Processing
- Wireless Communications
- Image and Video Processing
- Control Systems
- Computational Finance
- Computational Biology

Other: _____

12. The last time I programmed in MATLAB or a similar language was... *

Mark only one oval.

- less than 1 year ago.
- between 1 to 4 years ago.
- over 4 years ago.

13. On which operating systems are your development environments? *

Select one or more options.

Tick all that apply.

- Windows
- Unix / Linux
- macOS

Other: _____

14. I use only the command window when working with MATLAB. *

As opposed to working with executable text files containing code.

Mark only one oval.

- True, I use only the command window. Skip to question 27
- False, I use the command window to solve small problems or to complement my coding (e.g. inspecting variables, testing functions, etc.).
- False, I never use the command window.

This section focuses on the importance you give to the reusability of your programs.

15. When I develop a program in MATLAB, I always try to make it easily reusable and maintainable. *

Mark only one oval.

	1	2	3	4	5	
Strongly disagree	<input type="radio"/>	Strongly agree				

16. I expect to be the sole user of my MATLAB programs. *

Mark only one oval.

	1	2	3	4	5	
Strongly disagree	<input type="radio"/>	Strongly agree				

17. In the past, I've had to maintain a MATLAB program for over a year. *

Mark only one oval.

	1	2	3	4	5	
Strongly disagree	<input type="radio"/>	Strongly agree				

18. My MATLAB programs tend to have... *

Mark only one oval.

- only 1 m-file.
- 2 to 5 m-files.
- 6 to 10 m-files.
- 11 to 20 m-files.
- 21 to 50 m-files.
- more than 50 m-files.

19. The m-files I deal with tend to have... *

Mark only one oval.

- only 1 function.
- 2 to 5 functions.
- 6 to 10 functions.
- more than 10 functions.

This final section concerns your use of the language, as well as your level of satisfaction with that use.

20. Regarding MATLAB's modules, in my programs I use...

Modules are the distinct units that enclose the code related to a specific functionality.

Tick all that apply.

- Classes
- Enumerations
- Functions
- M-files
- Objects

21. I try to find and minimise the use of duplicated code across the various m-files.

*

Mark only one oval.

	1	2	3	4	5	
Strongly disagree	<input type="radio"/>	Strongly agree				

22. I often think about modularity when I'm working with MATLAB. *

Modularity is the approach of organizing a program into multiple modules (e.g., m-files, functions, classes or objects).

Mark only one oval.

	1	2	3	4	5	
Strongly disagree	<input type="radio"/>	Strongly agree				

23. I am satisfied with MATLAB's current support to modularity. *

Modularity is the approach of organizing a program into multiple modules (e.g., m-files, functions, classes or objects).

Mark only one oval.

	1	2	3	4	5	
Strongly disagree	<input type="radio"/>	Strongly agree				

24. When maintaining a MATLAB program, I don't have any trouble understanding the code or its structure. *

Mark only one oval.

	1	2	3	4	5	
Strongly disagree	<input type="radio"/>	Strongly agree				

25. Regarding typical uses of MATLAB, I consider MATLAB's strongest competitor to be... *

Mark only one oval.

- Octave
- SciLab
- RLab
- Python
- R
- Other: _____

26. I use object-orientation features when programming in other languages. *

Languages that are not MATLAB, Rlab, Scilab or Octave.

Mark only one oval.

- True
- False

Thank you for your contribution!

27. If you wish to receive the results of the study via e-mail, feel free to leave your email address in the text field below.

28. If you wish to participate in a future questionnaire surrounding this research, feel free to leave your email address in the text field below.

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